

Managing task and assignment in Google Class Room

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Fajar Purwatmiasih

How to create assignment, edit assignment, and give feedback.

Will be presented by Eri Nurianti

Creating Assignment

1. Enter the name and description of your task.

Technology Application and Software Worksheet

This application will identify types of hardware by picture and will list types of application and operating software.

December 30, 2014 Add time

STREAM

STUDENTS

ABOUT

Hardware and Software Worksheet

Students will identify types of hardware by picture and will list types of application and operating system software.

Due Dec 19, 2014 1:00 AM

Hardware & Software Worksheet (...)
Google Docs

Make a copy for each student

Technology Applicatio...

CANCEL

ASSIGN

Announcement Assignment

7. Check that all information is right and press **ASSIGN**.

ASSIGN

Edit your Assignment

DUE DEC 19, 1:00 AM

Edit

ONE

Delete

Choose which one that you want to edit

Hardware and Software Worksheet ✓

Students will identify types of hardware by picture and will list types of application and operating system software. ✓

Due Dec 19, 2014 1:00 AM X ✓

Hardware & Software Worksheet (Assignment) X
Google Docs

Each student will get a copy X

📎 🔄 🎥 ☰ ✓

CANCEL SAVE

The screenshot shows a Google Classroom assignment card. The top section contains the assignment title 'Hardware and Software Worksheet' with a green checkmark, a description 'Students will identify types of hardware by picture and will list types of application and operating system software.' with a green checkmark, and a due date 'Due Dec 19, 2014 1:00 AM' with a red 'X' and a green checkmark. The bottom section shows the assignment is linked to 'Hardware & Software Worksheet (Assignment)' and 'Google Docs', both with red 'X' marks, and 'Each student will get a copy' also with a red 'X'. At the bottom, there are icons for attachments, a refresh button, a video icon, a menu icon, and a green checkmark. On the right, there are 'CANCEL' and 'SAVE' buttons.

Give Feedback to your students

RETURNED Sep 6, 11:55 AM
See submission history

Add private comment...

Select which assignment and then select the name of student.

2. Where it says **Private comments**, write a message to the student and then click **POST**.

 Add private comment...

3. The student will be able to respond to the explanations you have given.
-

How to give scores, edit scores and downloading scores in Google Classroom

This materials will be presented by Fajar Purwatmiasih

Give scores to your Students

ASSIGNMENT Sep 5

Hardware / Software Worksheet

16 DONE

DUE SEP 5

6 NOT DONE

Hardware & Software Worksheet (Assignment)
Google Docs

Each student will get a copy

 Add comment...

The image shows a Google Classroom assignment card. At the top, it says 'ASSIGNMENT Sep 5'. The main title of the assignment is 'Hardware / Software Worksheet', which is circled in green with a hand cursor pointing to it. To the right of the title, there are two statistics: '16 DONE' and '6 NOT DONE'. Above the '6 NOT DONE' is a red label 'DUE SEP 5' with a vertical ellipsis menu icon. Below the main title, there is a section for the assignment details, including a small icon of a Google Docs document, the title 'Hardware & Software Worksheet (Assignment)', the file type 'Google Docs', and the note 'Each student will get a copy'. At the bottom of the card, there is a comment section with a user profile picture and the text 'Add comment...'.

ASSIGNMENT Sep 2

DUE SEP 5

Hardware / Software Worksheet

6
NOT DONE

Hardware & Software Worksheet (Assignment)
Google Docs

Each student will get a copy

Add comment...

Select the which student that you want to score

<input type="checkbox"/>	7th BMS [redacted] Send a note	RETURNED	9/10
<input type="checkbox"/>	7th BMS [redacted] Send a note	RETURNED	8/10
<input type="checkbox"/>	7th BMS [redacted] Send a note	LATE	<input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/> <input type="radio"/>
<input type="checkbox"/>	7th BMS [redacted] Send a note	RETURNED	9/10
<input type="checkbox"/>	7th BMS [redacted] Send a note	RETURNED	10/10
<input type="checkbox"/>	7th BMS [redacted] Send a note	LATE	No Grace

you can give label and coment to your students in their file directly

Computer Hardware & Software
Technology Applications
Chapter 1 Lesson 1

ns: Answer each question below by typing in your response. If you need help in answering the questions use your textbook pages 2-4)

are

each piece of computer hardware.

	Part	Name
A.		desktop pc
B.		keyboard

Select returned to give back the file to the students

RETURNED

8/10

LATE

No Grade

RETURNED

9/10

Do teacher can change the score? Is it possible?

Changing Points is Possible

1. Open the assignment you want to the set points for. Locate the **Points** box in the top-right corner.

2. You can either click the drop-down arrow next to the point value and pick the number, or you can click on **10** and enter the value you want to assign.

3. Click **Fix** when asked if you are sure you want to update the value of the amount.

Update point value

Are you sure you want to update the point value of this assignment?

Students who have already received grades will be notified.

CANCEL

UPDATE

Downloading Students Grade

- Open Assignment
- Find download
- You can save that to your computer then..

Downloading Student Grades

1. Open the assignment for which you would like to access the score. Find the **DOWNLOAD** button at the top of the list.

2. Click the button to either access **This assignment** or **All assignments**.

Thank you!